

BUCKLING AND POSTBUCKLING ANALYSIS OF DELAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

The buckling and postbuckling behaviors of delaminated composite beam-plates with arbitrary anisotropy of elasticity under compression are studied by an analytical solution and an asymptotic analysis. An expression for the potential energy release rates associated with the delamination growth is obtained. The data of the experiment conducted on isotropic laminates agree well with the predictions by the analytical solution.

Keywords : delaminated plate, delamination buckling, potential energy release rate

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that delaminations of composite laminates, which are due to transverse low-velocity impact of foreign objects, can greatly reduce the load-carrying capacity of the laminates in compression. The delaminated area may buckle at low compressive load and subsequently spread, leading to the catastrophic failure of the plates. The buckling and postbuckling behaviors of delaminated orthotropic beam-plates were investigated analytically by Yin, Sallan and Simitses[1]. In the present paper, we analyze the behaviors of axially compressed delaminated anisotropic beam-plates taking into account inplane shear deformation due to the anisotropy of the delaminated area. And the potential energy release rates associated with the delamination growth are obtained. The asymptotic analysis is also conducted based on the perturbation method. The analytical solutions are verified by the experiment performed on anisotropic laminates.

2. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

We consider a compressed beam-plate of a length 2ℓ and thickness t_1 having both ends clamped as shown in Figure 1. The delamination of a length $2a$ located at a height t_2 above the lower surface is assumed to be present throughout the width of the plate.

2.1 Strain-displacement relations

By using the symmetry condition with respect to the midpoint $x=0$, we only analyze the half of the plate ($x \geq 0$). The delamination divides the plate to undelaminated region 1 and lower and upper delaminated regions 2, 3 as shown in Figure 1. Since the z coordinates of the midplanes of the three regions are determined as shown in Figure 2, the height ζ_i from the midplanes are given by

$$\zeta_1 = z \quad \zeta_2 = z + \frac{t_3}{2} \quad \zeta_3 = z - \frac{t_2}{2} \quad (1)$$

It follows from the Kirchhoff hypothesis that the displacements at $\zeta_i = \zeta_i$ are expressed in terms of the midplane displacements u_i , v_i and w_i as

$$u_i(\zeta_i) = u_i - \zeta_i \frac{dw_1}{dx} \quad v_i(\zeta_i) = v_i \quad w_i(\zeta_i) = w_i \quad (2)$$

Then, the strains take the form

$$\varepsilon_{xi} = \varepsilon_i + \zeta_i \kappa_i \quad \varepsilon_{yi} = 0 \quad \gamma_{xyi} = \gamma_i \quad (3)$$

where

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{du_i}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dw_i}{dx} \right)^2 \quad \gamma_i = \frac{dv_i}{dx} \quad \kappa_i = -\frac{d^2 w_i}{dx^2} \quad (4)$$

2.2 Constitutive equations

The stress-strain relations of the region i are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix}_i \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}_i \quad (5)$$

Substitution of Equation 3 into Equation 5 yields

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_i + \zeta_i \kappa_i \\ \gamma_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \zeta_i \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_i \\ \gamma_i \\ \kappa_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The generalized stresses per unit width are defined as

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \end{bmatrix}_i = \int \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ \zeta_i & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}_i d\zeta_i = \begin{bmatrix} N_i \\ L_i \\ M_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Substituting Equations 6 into Equation 7, we have the constitutive equations expressed in terms of the generalized stresses and the generalized strains as

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_i \\ L_i \\ M_i \end{bmatrix} = \int \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{11}\zeta_i \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{66} & \bar{Q}_{16}\zeta_i \\ \bar{Q}_{11}\zeta_i & \bar{Q}_{16}\zeta_i & \bar{Q}_{11}\zeta_i^2 \end{bmatrix} d\zeta_i \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_i \\ \gamma_i \\ \kappa_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{N_i} & A_{C_i} & B_{N_i} \\ A_{C_i} & A_{L_i} & B_{L_i} \\ B_{N_i} & B_{L_i} & D_i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_i \\ \gamma_i \\ \kappa_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

2.3 Principle of stationary potential energy

The potential energy for the half of the plate takes the form

$$\Pi = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_i (N_i \varepsilon_i + L_i \gamma_i + M_i \kappa_i) dx + P u_1 \Big|_{x=\ell} \quad (9)$$

We prescribe the displacement boundary conditions as

$$x = 0; \quad \frac{dw_2}{dx} = \frac{dw_3}{dx} = 0 \quad u_2 = u_3 = 0 \quad v_2 = v_3 = 0 \quad (10)$$

the symmetry conditions for displacement as

$$x = \ell; \quad w_1 = 0 \quad \frac{dw_1}{dx} = 0 \quad v_1 = 0 \quad (11)$$

and the displacement continuity conditions at the delamination tip as

$$\begin{aligned} x = a; \quad u_2 &= u_1 + \frac{t_3}{2} \frac{dw_1}{dx}, & u_3 &= u_1 - \frac{t_2}{2} \frac{dw_1}{dx} \\ v_2 &= v_3 = v_1, & \frac{dw_2}{dx} &= \frac{dw_3}{dx} = \frac{dw_1}{dx} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The principle of stationary potential energy with the prescribed conditions given by Equations 10, 11 and 12 yields

$$\begin{aligned} 0 = \delta\Pi &= \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_i \left\{ N_i \left(\frac{d\delta u_i}{dx} + \frac{dw_i}{dx} \frac{d\delta w_i}{dx} \right) + L_i \frac{d\delta v_i}{dx} - M_i \frac{d^2 \delta w_i}{dx^2} \right\} dx + P \delta u_1 \Big|_{x=\ell} \\ &= - \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_i \left[\frac{dN_i}{dx} \delta u_i + \frac{dL_i}{dx} \delta v_i + \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \left(N_i \frac{dw_i}{dx} + \frac{dM_i}{dx} \right) \right\} \delta w_i \right] dx \\ &\quad - \sum \left[N_i \delta u_i + L_i \delta v_i + \left(N_i \frac{dw_i}{dx} + \frac{dM_i}{dx} \right) \delta w_i + M_i \left(-\frac{d\delta w_i}{dx} \right) \right]_{x=0} \\ &\quad + \left[(N_2 + N_3 - N_1) \delta u_i + (L_2 + L_3 - L_1) \delta v_i \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left\{ \left(N_2 \frac{dw_2}{dx} + \frac{dM_2}{dx} \right) + \left(N_3 \frac{dw_3}{dx} + \frac{dM_3}{dx} \right) - \left(N_1 \frac{dw_1}{dx} + \frac{dM_1}{dx} \right) \right\} \delta w_i \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left\{ \left(M_2 - N_2 \frac{t_3}{2} \right) + \left(M_3 + N_3 \frac{t_2}{2} \right) - M_1 \right\} \left(-\frac{d\delta w_i}{dx} \right) \right]_{x=a} \\ &\quad + \left[(N_1 + P) \delta u_1 + L_1 \delta v_1 + \left(N_1 \frac{dw_1}{dx} + \frac{dM_1}{dx} \right) \delta w_1 + M_1 \left(-\frac{dw_1}{dx} \right) \right]_{x=\ell} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

From Equation 13, we have the equilibrium equations as

$$\frac{dN_i}{dx} = 0 \quad \frac{dL_i}{dx} = 0 \quad \frac{d}{dx} \left(N_i \frac{dw_i}{dx} + \frac{dM_i}{dx} \right) = 0 \quad (14)$$

the stress symmetry conditions as

$$x = 0; \quad N_2 \frac{dw_2}{dx} + \frac{dM_2}{dx} = N_3 \frac{dw_3}{dx} + \frac{dM_3}{dx} = 0 \quad (15)$$

the stress boundary conditions as

$$x = \ell; \quad N_1 + P = 0 \quad (16)$$

and the stress continuity conditions at the delamination tip as

$$\begin{aligned} x = a; \quad N_2 + N_3 - N_1 &= 0 & L_2 + L_3 - L_1 &= 0 \\ \left(N_2 \frac{dw_2}{dx} + \frac{dM_2}{dx} \right) + \left(N_3 \frac{dw_3}{dx} + \frac{dM_3}{dx} \right) - \left(N_1 \frac{dw_1}{dx} + \frac{dM_1}{dx} \right) &= 0 \\ \left(M_2 - N_2 \frac{t_3}{2} \right) + \left(M_3 + N_3 \frac{t_2}{2} \right) - M_1 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

3. PREBUCKLING AND POSTBUCKLING STATES

For the uniform prebuckling state, we have

$$v_{i0} = w_{i0} = 0 \quad \gamma_{i0} = \kappa_{i0} = 0 \quad N_{i0} = -P \quad (18)$$

Then, Equation 8 gives

$$\varepsilon_{i0} = -\frac{P}{A_{N_i}} \quad u_{i0} = -\frac{P}{A_{N_i}} x \quad (19)$$

and

$$N_{i0} = -\frac{A_{N_i}}{A_{N_i}} P \quad L_{i0} = -\frac{A_{C_i}}{A_{N_i}} P \quad M_{i0} = -\frac{B_{N_i}}{A_{N_i}} P \quad (20)$$

On using Equations 18, 19 and 20, we now express the stresses, strains and displacements as

$$\begin{aligned} N_i &= N_{i0} + N_i^* & L_i &= L_{i0} + L_i^* & M_i &= M_{i0} + M_i^* \\ \varepsilon_i &= \varepsilon_{i0} + \varepsilon_i^* & \gamma_i &= \gamma_{i0} + \gamma_i^* & \kappa_i &= \kappa_{i0} + \kappa_i^* \\ u_i &= u_{i0} + u_i^* & v_i &= v_{i0} + v_i^* & w_i &= w_{i0} + w_i^* \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where the superscript "*" is pertaining to the deviation of the buckling state value from the prebuckling state one.

Substituting Equation 21 into Equations 8, 10, 11, 12, 14,15,16 and 17, we have the governing equations and the boundary and continuity conditions expressed in terms of the deviation values.

4. ANALYTICAL SOLUTION

Setting the stress state as

$$N_1^* = 0 \quad N_2^* = -p \quad N_3^* = p \quad L_1^* = s_2 + s_3 \quad L_2^* = s_2 \quad L_3^* = s_3 \quad (22)$$

we can obtain the analytical solution of the governing equations derived in Chapter 3 for a given p .

5. POTENTIAL ENERGY RELEASE RATE

By differentiating Equation 9 with respect to the delamination length a and utilizing the transversality condition at the delamination tip, we obtain the analytical expression for the potential energy release rate associated with the delamination growth as

$$\begin{aligned} G &= -\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial a} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_i \frac{\partial}{\partial a} (N_i \varepsilon_i + L_i \gamma_i + M_i \kappa_i) dx \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \left[N_1 \varepsilon_1 + L_1 \gamma_1 + M_1 \kappa_1 - \sum_{i=2}^3 (N_i \varepsilon_i + L_i \gamma_i + M_i \kappa_i) \right]_{x=a} - P \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial a} \Big|_{x=l} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[-N_1 \varepsilon_1 - L_1 \gamma_1 - M_1 \kappa_1 + \sum_{i=2}^3 (N_i \varepsilon_i + L_i \gamma_i + M_i \kappa_i) \right]_{x=a} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[-N_1^* \varepsilon_1^* - L_1^* \gamma_1^* - M_1^* \kappa_1^* + \sum_{i=2}^3 (N_i^* \varepsilon_i^* + L_i^* \gamma_i^* + M_i^* \kappa_i^*) \right]_{x=a} \quad (23) \end{aligned}$$

6. ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTION

Assuming that the beam-plate exhibits the bifurcation at the critical load P_{cr} , we write the expansion of the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_i^* \\ L_i^* \\ M_i^* \\ \varepsilon_i^* \\ \gamma_i^* \\ \kappa_i^* \\ u_i^* \\ v_i^* \\ w_i^* \\ P - P_{cr} \end{bmatrix} = e \begin{bmatrix} N_{i1} \\ L_{i1} \\ M_{i1} \\ \varepsilon_{i1} \\ \gamma_{i1} \\ \kappa_{i1} \\ u_{i1} \\ v_{i1} \\ w_{i1} \\ P_1 \end{bmatrix} + e^2 \begin{bmatrix} N_{i2} \\ L_{i2} \\ M_{i2} \\ \varepsilon_{i2} \\ \gamma_{i2} \\ \kappa_{i2} \\ u_{i2} \\ v_{i2} \\ w_{i2} \\ P_2 \end{bmatrix} + e^3 \begin{bmatrix} N_{i3} \\ L_{i3} \\ M_{i3} \\ \varepsilon_{i3} \\ \gamma_{i3} \\ \kappa_{i3} \\ u_{i3} \\ v_{i3} \\ w_{i3} \\ P_3 \end{bmatrix} + \dots \quad (24)$$

Substitution of Equation 24 into the governing equations and the boundary and continuity conditions derived in Chapter 2 gives the equations of the j -th order as the coefficient of e^j . The linear j -th order equations can be solved by using the orthogonality conditions as

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \int_i \left\{ \frac{1}{2} N_{i1} \frac{dw_{ik}}{dx} \frac{dw_{i,j+1-k}}{dx} - \left(\frac{A_{N_i} P_k - N_{ik}}{A_{N_i}} \right) \frac{dw_{i1}}{dx} \frac{dw_{i,j+1-k}}{dx} \right\} dx = 0 \quad (25)$$

7. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The numerical calculations were performed for beam-plates with $t_1=2.6\text{mm}$ and $\ell=150\text{mm}$. Two kinds of laminates were selected to study the buckling and postbuckling behaviors;

(1) Isotropic aluminium alloy laminates with

$$t_3 / t_1 = 0.231 \quad \bar{a} = a / \ell = 0.0, 0.3, 0.6, 0.7$$

(2) Graphite-epoxy $[0^\circ/90^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$ and $[45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminates with

$$t_3 / t_1 = 0.250 \quad \bar{a} = a / \ell = 0.0, 0.4, 0.8$$

The analytical relations between the load ($\bar{P} = P/A_{N_1}$) and the end shortening

($\bar{U} = -u_1|_{x=\ell}/\ell$) for the graphite-epoxy laminates and for the isotropic aluminium alloy laminates are shown in Figures 3 and 4, respectively. In Figure 4, the asymptotic solutions based on the perturbation second order are also indicated. It can be seen that the asymptotic solutions represent the initial postbuckling behaviors.

The contour plots of the potential energy release rate ($\bar{G} = G/A_{N_1}$) in the load-end shortening plane are shown in Figure 5 together with the paths of plates with constant delamination lengths for the aluminium alloy laminates. If the critical potential energy release rate of a laminate is

$\bar{G}_{cr} = 3.0 \times 10^{-8}$, the delamination grows at an intersection of the $\bar{P} - \bar{U}$ curve with the

$\bar{G}_{cr} = 3.0 \times 10^{-8}$ curve. A laminate with the delamination length of $\bar{a} = 0.3$ exhibits a catastrophic delamination growth at the intersection in a load-controlled test. However in an end shortening-controlled test, at the intersection the delamination length increases quasi-statically so that the

$\bar{G}_{cr} = 3.0 \times 10^{-8}$ curve is followed until it becomes $\bar{a} = 0.5$ where the laminate shows a catastrophic failure.

8. EXPERIMENT

The buckling test was conducted on isotropic aluminium alloy laminates with both ends clamped as shown in Figure 6. The load-end shortening curves are included in Figure 4. The

experimental data agree well with the analytical solutions. The delamination growths were not observed because the potential energy release rates associated with the delamination growth at deformation range in the test as shown in Figure 5 are much smaller than the critical energy release rate.

The relations between the load ($\bar{P} = P/A_{N_1}$) and the deflections ($\bar{w} = w/\ell$) at three points of a specimen are represented in Figure 7 together with the theoretical predictions for a laminate with $\bar{a} = 0.5$. The relations between the load ($\bar{P} = P/A_{N_1}$) and the inplane loads ($\bar{N}_i = N_i/A_{N_1}$) are shown in Figure 8 for a laminate with $\bar{a} = 0.5$. The region 3 sustains only small amount of total load after the buckling. The experimental data shown in Figures 7 and 8 give good agreement with the analytical solutions.

9. CONCLUSIONS

An analytical solution and an asymptotic one were obtained for the buckling and postbuckling behavior of delaminated beam-plates with arbitrary anisotropy of elasticity in compression. The theoretical predictions were verified by the experiment conducted on isotropic laminates.

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Figure 1. Delaminated beam-plate.

Figure 2. Midplanes of undelaminated region 1 and delaminated regions 2, 3.

Figure 3. Relation between load \bar{P} and end shortening \bar{U} for graphite-epoxy laminates.

Figure 4. Relation between load \bar{P} and end shortening \bar{U} for isotropic aluminum alloy laminates.

Figure 5. Relation between load \bar{P} and end shortening \bar{U} and contour plots of energy release rate \bar{G} for isotropic aluminum alloy laminates.

Figure 6. Specimens ; isotropic aluminum alloy laminates.

Figure 7. Relation between load \bar{P} and deflections \bar{w} for isotropic aluminum alloy laminates : $\bar{a} = 0.5$.

Figure 8. Relation between load \bar{P} and inplane loads \bar{N}_i for isotropic aluminum alloy laminates : $\bar{a} = 0.5$.